

Rispondere senza sapere: Discursive Strategies* of Large Language Models Under Information Scarcity.

The Case of *Fanciulla di Vagli*

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Abstract

This work analyzes the discursive strategies adopted by five Large Language Models (LLMs) when they are queried about poorly documented knowledge subjects. Through a case study — the *Fanciulla di Vagli* — the responses of different closed-source models to a single prompt are examined, considering factual accuracy, discursive strategies, and source attribution.

The results show that, under conditions of information scarcity, models tend to fill informational gaps through referential substitutions, culturally plausible narratives, and assertively formulated inferences. Requesting sources does not necessarily guarantee greater correctness; instead, it often introduces forms of post-hoc legitimization, such as non-binding citations or simulated bibliographic apparatuses.

The case thus highlights a systematic gap between discursive plausibility and epistemic verifiability.

Keywords: Large Language Models (LLM); LLM hallucinations; discursive strategies; low-information contexts; source attribution; epistemic authority; *Fanciulla di Vagli*.

*In this work, the term "discursive strategies" is used to denote recurring configurations of linguistic and structural choices, independently of any form of intentionality on the part of the system.

1 Introduction

In recent years, *Large Language Models* (LLMs) have established themselves as central tools in accessing and mediating digital knowledge. Integrated into search engines, virtual assistants, and decision-support systems, these models are increasingly perceived as authoritative sources of information, capable of providing fluent, coherent, and often convincing answers on a wide variety of subjects.

However, this discursive authority does not necessarily coincide with genuine availability of knowledge. Generative language models do not directly query a structured database, nor do they possess an explicit representation of the limits of their own competence. Instead, they operate through the probabilistic generation of linguistic sequences, based on regularities learned during the training phase. In this context, when a subject is poorly documented or underrepresented in the training data, the model finds itself in the position of having to respond *without knowing*.

This work is situated within a broader reflection on the ways in which LLMs produce responses under conditions of informational uncertainty, examining the discursive strategies through which such systems fill knowledge gaps and construct textual reliability even in the absence of solid data.

To address these questions, this paper examines a specific case study: the *Fanciulla di Vagli*. This is a burial containing the remains of a cremation, placed in a cinerary urn and incorporated into a Ligurian-Apuan funerary monument from the early decades of the second century BC. Discovered in 2008 near the cemetery of Vagli di Sopra, the context is the subject of a Wikipedia entry created by the author in 2016¹, and is characterized by limited circulation of online secondary sources. Starting from an apparently simple question — "*What is the Fanciulla di Vagli?*" — the responses provided by several closed LLMs are analyzed, comparing their content, factual accuracy, argumentative style, and handling of sources.

The aim is not to evaluate model performance in terms of absolute correctness, but to observe the way in which they construct discourse under conditions of information scarcity. In particular, attention is focused on errors, inaccuracies, and any *hallucinations*, understood not only as false statements but as linguistic strategies of filling, normalization, and legitimization of produced knowledge.

Through a qualitative analysis of the responses and a manual verification of the cited sources, this work aims to show how, in the absence of consolidated knowledge, LLMs tend to draw on pre-existing narrative and cultural schemas, privileging plausibility over verifiability. In this sense, the case of the *Fanciulla di Vagli* be-

¹https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fanciulla_di_Vagli

comes a privileged observatory for reflecting on the relationship between artificial intelligence, epistemic authority, and knowledge construction in the contemporary digital ecosystem.

A potential critical point of the framework concerns systems that declare (or can activate) web browsing or external *retrieval* functionalities. In such cases, the experiment would no longer measure solely what the model "knows" by virtue of its training, but also its capacity to select, read, and synthesize sparse or fragmentary sources. A potentially incorrect response would therefore not be attributable solely to a limitation in training-set coverage, but could depend on interpretation errors, distorted synthesis, or discursive *overconfidence*.

This ambiguity cannot be definitively eliminated from the responses alone. However, it does not invalidate the analytical framework: in both cases — whether the model draws exclusively on prior knowledge or consults external sources — "information scarcity" remains an operative condition, manifesting either as the absence of consolidated data in training or as difficulty in locating and interpreting fragmentary evidence. What the analysis observes are the discursive strategies through which LLMs construct reliability under such conditions, regardless of the specific origin of the information.

2 Method

This work adopts a qualitative approach based on a case study, with the aim of observing and analyzing the discursive behavior of several Large Language Models (LLMs) in a situation of information scarcity. The analysis does not aim at a quantitative evaluation of performance, but at a critical understanding of the linguistic and argumentative strategies adopted by the models when called upon to respond to a question concerning a poorly documented object of knowledge.

2.1 Selection of the Case Study

The case study selected is the *Fanciulla di Vagli*. The choice of this subject is motivated by three main factors: the limited diffusion of online secondary sources, the specialized nature of the topic, and the presence of an encyclopedic entry that serves as a verifiable reference for the analysis of responses.

The *Fanciulla di Vagli* thus represents an example of digital knowledge that is scarcely represented in the web's information ecosystem — particularly well suited to highlighting any gaps, approximations, or filling strategies adopted by language models.

2.2 Research Question

All models considered were asked the same question, formulated in an intentionally simple and non-leading manner:

"What is the Fanciulla di Vagli?"

The choice of an open-ended question aimed at obtaining a basic description allows for free observation of the ways in which each model constructs its response, without format constraints or contextual cues.

In a second phase, following the initial question, an explicit request was submitted for the sources used, in order to analyze the models' behavior with respect to the epistemic justification of the information provided.

2.3 Model Selection and Corpus Construction

The analysis was conducted on a limited number of closed LLMs, selected for their widespread use and the availability of *web chat* interfaces. Specifically, the models analyzed were DeepSeek-V3, ChatGPT-4o, Gemini 3, Claude Sonnet 4.5, and Mistral Large. The choice of closed models reflects a realistic and widespread usage condition, in which it is not possible to access either the training data or the internal mechanisms of operation.

For each model, one response was collected, keeping the prompt formulation unchanged and without providing additional context or external documentation.

The responses generated by the models constitute the textual corpus analyzed in this study. All outputs were transcribed in full and preserved without modification.

2.4 Analytical Criteria

The analysis of the responses was conducted manually according to a qualitative grid, articulated along four main dimensions:

- **Factual accuracy:** correspondence of the statements provided with the verifiable information present in the Wikipedia entry and available sources.
- **Discursive strategies:** rhetorical and narrative modes adopted by the models, such as assertive tone, epistemic caution, use of analogies, or standard encyclopedic structures.
- **Source management:** presence or absence of explicit references, distinction between real, vague, or unverifiable sources.

- **Error typology:** identification of inaccuracies, undue generalizations, or forms of *hallucination*, both factual and source-related.

These criteria allow for a comparative analysis of the responses that takes into account not only the correctness of the information, but also the ways in which knowledge is constructed and presented.

2.5 Methodological Limitations

It should be noted that this study does not allow for generalizable conclusions about the functioning of LLMs in an absolute sense. The analysis is circumscribed to a single case study and a limited number of models. Furthermore, it is not possible to trace with certainty the training sources of the analyzed models; considerations regarding sources therefore remain interpretive and discursive in nature.

However, precisely because of its circumscribed and qualitative nature, the adopted method proves adequate for highlighting significant dynamics in the production of discourse by LLMs under conditions of information scarcity.

3 Analysis of Mistral Large

3.1 Description of the Response

The Mistral model describes the *Fanciulla di Vagli* as a steatite figurine dating back to the Copper Age (third millennium BC), discovered in 1957 during archaeological excavations in the Garfagnana. The response attributes a symbolic function related to fertility to the object, describes its style as stylized and geometric, and states that the artifact would be currently preserved at the Museo Archeologico Nazionale in Florence.

The response is organized in a structured manner and follows a typically encyclopedic framework, including an initial definition, a list of main characteristics, and a final institutional placement.

3.2 Error Analysis

Comparison with verifiable information reveals a sharp and systematic discrepancy.

The model's response does not present simple inaccuracies but proposes an entirely alternative reconstruction of the object of knowledge. The nature of the find is completely altered: from a cinerary urn inserted into a Ligurian-Apuan funerary monument of the Republican era, to a prehistoric figurine associated with fertility

cults. The date of discovery (1957 instead of 2008) and the place of preservation are also invented.

The observed error can be classified as a form of *substitution by cultural analogy*. The type of object evoked by the model is not arbitrary. Several prehistoric steatite figurines are indeed known in Italy, found in contexts such as Savignano², Massaciucoli³, and Lake Bracciano, generally attributed to the Paleolithic or Neolithic. However, no attestations of artifacts of this type exist either in Vagli or, more generally, in the Garfagnana area. The model therefore appears to draw on a real and culturally consolidated archaeological repertoire, relocating it inappropriately with respect to the specific geographical and chronological context.

The model does not provide a vague or partially incorrect response but substitutes the entire referent with another plausible archaeological object, drawing on an iconographic and narrative repertoire that is widespread in historical and archaeological popular discourse. In this sense, the Fanciulla di Vagli is not described incorrectly but is effectively *recreated* as a different object, consistent with well-known cultural schemas.

3.3 Discursive Strategies

From a discursive standpoint, the response exhibits a high degree of plausibility. Specialized vocabulary (e.g., "steatite," "Copper Age," "Eneolithic") contributes to creating an effect of technical competence. The textual structure mirrors that of a museum catalogue entry or encyclopedic entry, further reinforcing the credibility of the response.

A particularly significant element is the reference to an authoritative cultural institution — the Museo Archeologico Nazionale in Florence — which serves a legitimizing function for the information. This reference, although unfounded, contributes to making the response persuasive to the non-specialist reader.

The response contains no element of epistemic caution. No expressions of uncertainty are used, nor is the possibility of incomplete knowledge acknowledged. On the contrary, the information is presented with confidence and assertiveness, despite being entirely unverifiable. The absence of doubt or caution reveals a tendency toward overconfidence, which is particularly problematic in contexts of information scarcity.

²The Venus of Savignano is currently on display at the Museo delle Civiltà in Rome

³The figurine is preserved at the Civici Musei di Villa Paolina, Museo Preistorico e Archeologico Alberto Carlo Blanc in Viareggio

3.4 Source Management

Following the explicit request to indicate the sources used, the model provided a list of references that includes the Wikipedia entry dedicated to the find, the institutional website Archeotoscana, and an article from the newspaper *Il Tirreno*. Unlike other cases of *improper source use*, the cited sources actually exist and are relevant to the subject of study.

However, a significant discrepancy emerges between the listed sources and the content of the previously provided response. The cited sources describe the Fanciulla di Vagli as a Ligurian-Apuan burial containing the remains of a cremation, datable to the early decades of the second century BC. In contrast, the response had presented the object as a prehistoric steatite figurine from the Copper Age. The citation of sources therefore occurs *post-hoc*, without any real derivational relationship between the mentioned documents and the content of the response. In this sense, we are not dealing with invented sources, but with the improper use of real sources as an instrument of discursive legitimization.

A further problematic element is represented by the formulation adopted by the model, which states that it "consulted" such sources. This expression suggests an activity of research and verification that cannot be reconstructed or verified from the provided response. Even assuming possible access to the cited sources, the discrepancy between the contents of the mentioned documents and the produced statements indicates that such sources did not play an informative role in the generated text.

This behavior can be interpreted as a form of rhetorical use of sources, in which real and relevant references are employed to legitimize content that does not derive from them. The model does not invent the sources but uses them as a discursive instrument to support a factually unfounded response. The presence of authoritative references does not reduce the error but contributes to masking it, increasing the risk of uncritical acceptance by the reader.

Under conditions of information scarcity, sources lose their function as instruments of epistemic control and are employed as elements of discursive legitimization.

4 Analysis of Claude Sonnet 4.5

4.1 Description of the Response

The Claude model identifies the Fanciulla di Vagli with the submerged bell tower of Fabbriche di Careggine, a medieval village that emerges from the waters of the artificial Lake of Vagli when the reservoir is drained. The response provides a

detailed description of the bell tower, the history of the submerged village, and the documented emergences over time.

The structure of the response is organized into thematic sections, with an orderly historical reconstruction and a list of the main emergences. The tone is informative and narratively effective, following a schema typical of historical-touristic popular discourse.

4.2 Error Analysis

The description provided is historically accurate with respect to the bell tower and the submerged village of Fabbriche di Careggine, but is completely incorrect with respect to the object of the question.

The error can be interpreted as a form of *referential confusion*, likely due to the geographical proximity and the strong symbolic association between the toponym "Vagli" and the submerged bell tower, one of the most well-known elements of the submerged village. In the absence of specific knowledge about the Fanciulla di Vagli, the model appears to have privileged a known referent, substituting the real but little-known object with one recognized in the collective imagination.

This type of error differs from a proper *hallucination* in the sense of invented content: the model does not create a non-existent object, but substitutes the correct referent with a real, well-known, and documented one. The semantic substitution exploits a symbolically strong object to fill an informational gap.

4.3 Discursive Strategies

From a discursive standpoint, the response is organized in an orderly and narratively effective manner. The subdivision into sections, the historical reconstruction, and the list of emergences contribute to reinforcing the credibility of the output. The language adopted is typical of quality cultural popular discourse: clear, accessible but not simplistic, with precise references to dates and events.

A particularly problematic element is the assertion that the submerged bell tower is "more commonly" known as the Fanciulla di Vagli. No historical, documentary, or local usage attestations can be found to support such a denomination. The use of the adverb "commonly" confers authority and apparent legitimacy to an incorrect identification, transforming a referential confusion into a presumed shared linguistic practice.

No signals of uncertainty or epistemic caution are present: the identification is presented as an established fact, without any qualification. This assertive confidence

contrasts with the nature of the error and shows how, in contexts of information scarcity, LLMs may privilege cultural and narrative prominence over referential precision.

4.4 Source Management

Following the request for clarification on the sources used, the model responded by declaring that it had relied exclusively on its training knowledge, specifying that such knowledge has a cutoff of January 2025. The model also noted the possible obsolescence of the information regarding the submerged bell tower of Fabbriche di Careggine and offered the possibility of conducting a web search to obtain more up-to-date data.

From a formal standpoint, this response appears epistemically correct. The model does not simulate a direct consultation of external sources but describes its own functioning in general terms, clarifying the temporal limits of its training and distinguishing between prior knowledge and real-time search. This behavior introduces a level of procedural transparency absent in other analyzed cases.

However, this correctness does not bear on the substantive error already observed. The response continues to identify the Fanciulla di Vagli with the submerged bell tower of Fabbriche di Careggine, maintaining unchanged the substitution previously analyzed. The explanation of the response generation process thus takes place entirely within an incorrect semantic frame.

This behavior can be interpreted as a form of *transparent but non-corrective explanation*: the model accurately explains how it produces knowledge and what its limits are, but does not question the identification of the object it is discussing. Transparency about functioning does not translate into a critical revision of the content.

From the user's perspective, such a response is particularly persuasive. The declaration of limitations, combined with the proposal for external verification, contributes to reinforcing the impression of reliability and competence, despite the factual error remaining unresolved. This case shows how, in Large Language Models, clear explanations of the model's functioning can coexist with content errors, and how a methodologically transparent presentation can render an incorrect response more credible.

5 Analysis of DeepSeek-V3

5.1 Description of the Response

The DeepSeek model interprets the Fanciulla di Vagli not as an archaeological find but as a legendary figure connected to the artificial Lake of Vagli and the submerged village of Fabbriche di Careggine. The response contains a narrative that interweaves real historical elements — such as the construction of the dam in 1947 and the submersion of the medieval village — with legendary components, including the existence of a young woman buried near the cemetery and the possibility that her ghost resurfaces when the water level drops.

The tone of the response is evocative and narrative, with explicit references to mystery and the fascination of the place. The structure follows a schema typical of folkloric narrative, with elements of collective memory and emotional suggestion.

5.2 Error Analysis

The model, in the absence of specific knowledge about the archaeological find known as the Fanciulla di Vagli, proposes a narrative structure drawing on a locally attested folkloric tradition.

The response evokes, without naming her, Teodora — a female figure who is an object of suspicion and distrust on the part of the community, in the collective memory of the hamlet of Fabbriche di Careggine, associated with the submersion of the village following the construction of the hydroelectric reservoir. This tradition has no historical or archaeological connection to the find known as the Fanciulla di Vagli.

The interpretation proposed by the model is also problematic at the lexical level. The legendary figure to which the response refers is an adult married woman, to whom the term "fanciulla" (maiden/young girl) is ill-suited.

The model's response contains no reference to the archaeological find, and the object of the question is reformulated exclusively in terms of a legendary tradition and a local narrative memory.

5.3 Discursive Strategies

From a discursive standpoint, the response presents itself explicitly as the narration of a local legend, adopting an evocative lexicon and making reference to territorial collective memory. This narrative mode is culturally plausible and coherent, but not pertinent to the specific object of the question.

5.4 Source Management

In response to the request to indicate the sources used, the DeepSeek model provides no specific references, but describes in general terms its own training process, invoking a general knowledge base of a historical, geographical, and folkloristic nature. The model declares that it has no access to specific sources or real-time data, introducing a level of procedural caution absent from the initial response.

In the absence of verifiable sources, the model refers to generic categories such as "local folklore," "popular articles," or "tourist guides," which do not allow for direct verification of the claims. The source thus becomes an indistinct discursive domain, with a consequent attenuation of epistemic responsibility. The final invitation to consult institutional bodies or local resources reinforces the impression of reliability, without however providing concrete tools for verification.

6 Analysis of ChatGPT-4o

6.1 Description of the Response

The ChatGPT-4o model identifies the Fanciulla di Vagli as a white Carrara marble statue, created in 2001 by Tuscan artist Giuliano Vangi and placed near the artificial Lake of Vagli as a commemorative monument to the victims⁴ of the submersion of the village of Fabbriche di Careggine. The response presents a detailed description of the work, its symbolic meaning, and the historical context to which it would be connected.

The structure of the response is articulated and narratively effective, with precise references to dates, proper names, and cultural contexts. The tone is that of specialized cultural popular discourse, with particular attention to the symbolic and commemorative aspects of the work.

6.2 Error Analysis

The description provided by the model is entirely invented: no statue by Giuliano Vangi dedicated to the Fanciulla di Vagli exists, nor are any commemorative projects linked to the archaeological find attested. The observed error can be interpreted as a form of fictional assembly of real elements, in which historically attested data (the submersion of Fabbriche di Careggine, the artificial Lake of Vagli, the existence of

⁴The submersion of the village did not, in fact, cause any victims.

sculptor Giuliano Vangi and cultural enhancement projects) are combined into a coherent but factually unfounded narrative.

This is not a simple confusion or a folkloric reworking, but the arbitrary attribution of a non-existent work of art to a real author and a plausible historical and cultural context. In this process, elements belonging to different disciplinary domains — archaeology, contemporary history, monumental art, and tourism promotion — are fused without distinction, producing a unified discourse that substitutes the archaeological referent with an imaginary artistic object.

6.3 Discursive Strategies

The ChatGPT-4o response adopts a narrative mode typical of cultural and commemorative popular discourse. The use of evocative language and visual and material details produces a strong effect of concreteness and plausibility.

A central element of the discursive strategy is the high apparent precision: dates, proper names, materials, and locations are provided with confidence, reinforcing the credibility of the output. This formal precision contributes to masking the fictional character of the described information.

The narrative follows consolidated rhetorical schemas associated with historical memory and territorial identity. In the absence of signals of epistemic caution, the model presents its reconstruction in a complete manner, privileging narrative coherence and cultural plausibility over factual correctness.

6.4 Source Management

Following the request to indicate the sources used, the ChatGPT-4o model declared that it had not consulted external sources in real time, specifying that the response is based on pre-trained knowledge up to 2024 and on data from publicly available sources.

The categories of sources mentioned include tourist and cultural websites dedicated to the Garfagnana and Tuscany, articles and guides on Vagli Sotto, the artificial Lake of Vagli, and the submerged village of Fabbriche di Careggine, general information on the work and the biography of sculptor Giuliano Vangi, as well as news from the Italian press regarding statues installed in Vagli and alleged cultural enhancement projects.

The response exhibits a form of procedural transparency: the model does not pretend to have consulted sources but openly declares relying on its training knowledge, specifying its temporal limits and offering the possibility of external verification.

However, this procedural correctness does not affect the validity of the informational content. The listed sources, while plausible and coherent with the proposed narrative, are not relevant to the actual referent of the Fanciulla di Vagli. The function of the cited sources is not to verify the content, but to consolidate an incorrect narrative construction.

The model does not resort to a single improper source, but constructs a network of generic references that are semantically and culturally coherent, rendering the response internally solid and persuasive. The plurality of sources and their apparent authority contribute to reinforcing the credibility of the output, making the underlying error less evident.

From the user’s perspective, this strategy produces a strong effect of reliability. The citation of broad categories of sources — however generic (institutional websites, press, tourist guides, artist biography) — suggests a thorough and multi-source research process, concealing the fact that the very object of the response is entirely invented. This case shows how, in Large Language Models, the citation of sources can serve a predominantly rhetorical function, stabilizing a plausible but factually incorrect discourse.

7 Analysis of Gemini 3

7.1 Description of the Response

Unlike previous models, Gemini correctly identifies the subject as an archaeological find and provides a description largely consistent with verifiable sources. The model correctly locates the discovery in October 2008, near the cemetery of Vagli di Sopra, and describes the Fanciulla di Vagli as a Ligurian-Apuan burial containing the remains of a cremation, attributable to a female individual between twelve and fourteen years of age.

The response provides a historical and cultural framing of the find, situating it within the context of the wars between Rome and the Ligurian Apuans in the second century BC and interpreting the burial as belonging to a family of high social rank. The structure of the text is clear and well organized, following a schema typical of quality archaeological popular discourse.

7.2 Error Analysis

Unlike the other models analyzed, Gemini does not produce relevant factual errors with respect to the verifiable data. The chronological context (early decades of the

second century BC), the type of find (burial with cinerary urn), the estimated age of the individual (twelve to fourteen years), and the association with the Ligurian Apuan population are substantially correct.

7.3 Discursive Strategies

From a discursive standpoint, Gemini's response adopts a style typical of quality historical popular discourse, characterized by a clear structure, accessible language, and an authoritative informative tone. The organization of the content and the thematic progression facilitate an effective understanding of the find and its context.

The main narrative strategy consists in the insertion of the find within a broader historical framework — in particular, that of the Romano-Ligurian wars of the second century BC. This contextualization is pertinent and contributes to enriching the interpretation of the discovery.

The interpretive components — relating to the social status of the young woman and the significance of the funerary assemblage — are introduced through probability markers and hypothetical formulations ("suggests that," "probably," "may have been"). However, such caution signals remain limited and do not affect the overall structure of the narrative, which presents itself as linear and conclusive. The model privileges a coherent and complete narrative, reducing the space for problematization and for the explicit acknowledgment of the margins of uncertainty inherent in archaeological interpretation.

7.4 Source Management

In response to the request to indicate the sources used, the Gemini model provides an articulated list of scientific publications, institutional bodies, and museums, presented with a structure and language typical of an academic bibliographic apparatus. This formulation confers a high perceived authority to the response.

The main critical point does not concern the plausibility of the cited sources or any recourse to external searches, but rather the lack of transparency in the relationship between sources and statements. The model does not explicitly address the connection between evidence and interpretations, nor does it systematically distinguish between attested data and inferences.

8 Conclusions

The comparative analysis of the responses produced by the different Large Language Models shows that the observed errors are not uniform but take different forms depending on the strategies adopted by the models. In some cases, a substitution of the referent with folklorically or symbolically well-known elements occurs; in others, the construction of plausible but nonexistent objects through the assembly of real data; in still others, the interpretive extension of correct information presented as consolidated knowledge.

A transversal element concerns the role of discursive strategies. Narrative coherence, authoritative tone, and the apparent precision of details contribute to making responses persuasive even in the presence of significant errors. The error does not manifest as hesitation or uncertainty, but as a response formulated with confidence and finality, without any trace of *hedging*. Models tend to offer complete and self-sufficient explanations that signal no margin of doubt and do not clearly distinguish between established facts and interpretations.

Another element concerns the relationship between the observed errors and the models' capacity to estimate their own uncertainty. LLMs are capable, at least under controlled conditions, of distinguishing between more or less reliable responses and of assigning a probability to the correctness of their own answers (Kadavath et al. 2022). However, the very nature of sequential text generation acts as a filter that flattens statistical uncertainty in favor of a syntactic fluency that is often deceptive.

The management of sources confirms this dynamic. The citation of real and plausible references does not guarantee the epistemic correctness of the content and may, in some cases, reinforce the credibility of incorrect responses. Even procedural transparency about the model's functioning does not necessarily translate into a critical revision of the output.

Overall, the study highlights how, under conditions of information scarcity, LLMs resort to culturally plausible substitution and narrative strategies. This points to the need for a critical approach that is not limited to factual verification, but considers the discursive modes through which knowledge is constructed and rendered reliable.

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